

WP3 Report

Metadata Working Group Recommendations

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EOSC Future Metadata Working Group recommendations

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Abstract

The purpose of a common rich metadata catalog schema is to facilitate discovery, contextualisation, access, interoperation and re-use of digital assets distributed across multiple repositories and described by heterogeneous metadata. Commonly – for research – the relevant assets are then orchestrated into a workflow to achieve a scientific purpose.

The Science Clusters – and the Research Infrastructures (RIs) within them – have a long history of providing access to large research and other communities through catalogs of digital assets. Representatives considered that the EOSC initially proposed catalog(s) (so-called 'profiles') were inadequate to describe the richness of the metadata available at the RIs describing digital assets which is necessary for end-users to obtain the relevant assets. Within WP3, two RI representatives (the authors) proposed a Metadata Working Group (MWG). This collected evidence from a rapid landscape survey using members of the WG and made initial recommendations, refined through WG meetings and discussions, to produce this document.

It became clear that a centralised, 'one size fits all' catalog for EOSC would not support the current working practices and evolving ambitions of the clusters. Furthermore, manual maintenance of such a 'catalog' is unsustainable. An architecture of peer-to-peer connections emerged from discussions, with the EOSC 'catalog' providing a 'mall' or 'zone' for the cluster RIs where each portal/catalog was represented with metadata, leading to the much more detailed – and scientifically relevant - metadata at the individual RI. This also ensured that access to assets involved agreeing to associated policies (e.g. licensing) and that acknowledgement/citation was managed.

The action in projects and other activities following-on from EOSC-Future (such as EOSC-Beyond) is to integrate this architecture and vision into the evolving EOSC architecture with its 'catalog' structure of profiles.

Version History

Version	Date	Authors/Contributors	Description
Vo.9	Dec 2023	Keith Jeffrey, Daan Broeder	Approved draft
V1.0	Jan 2024	Keith Jeffrey, Daan Broeder	EOSC future template applied, Released for publication

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1 Background

The Metadata Working Group (MWG) was set up with a charter within WP₃ of EOSC-Future¹. The basic objective was to recommend a FAIR² metadata element set appropriate to engage further and more deeply the Research Infrastructures (RIs) within the science clusters.

2 The Challenge

The research communities (RCs) formed around the RIs in the clusters have – in general and especially in the RIs established as ERICs³ – production-level facilities to discover, contextualise and access digital assets (DAs) of relevance to them and – in some cases – orchestrate and deploy workflows utilising those DAs. The RCs have monitored EOSC developments and in some cases individual RIs and individual data centres have provided metadata for the EOSC ‘catalog’ following the metadata schema from the EOSC profiles to describe their DAs but only on an investigative basis (and to increase visibility) – not for research production. The challenge of providing the required metadata ‘manually’ is not scalable and currently harvesting (except through OpenAIRE) is unavailable.

Based on recent EOSC-Future results and the already existing community RIs and the RC needs we see a challenge to facilitate use of EOSC by RCs around the RIs and clusters so that (a) EOSC provides a discovery and access route to especially the huge number of DAs already provided by the RC RIs for use by academia, industry and publicly-funded bodies; (b) the RCs have access to DAs of other RIs of relevance for cross- and multi-disciplinary research work; (c) (and a supplementary benefit mentioned by some RIs) the RCs have easy access to high performance computing facilities to permit more advanced research processes utilising analytics and simulations requiring computing capacity otherwise unavailable to them.

3 Required Architecture

The RCs have long suggested that the current centralised architecture of EOSC (one central federation ‘catalog’ enabling RI catalogues to push & pull resources⁴) is challenged and needs improvements because of (a) difficulty to maintain currency (being up-to-date); (b) governance and management of access to DAs; (c) over-generality thus losing valuable information needed by the RCs to discover and utilise the DAs. The RCs – through MWG - proposed that EOSC should have a zone or ‘mall’ with metadata describing existing RI portals and catalogs. This – along with other changing requirements and architectural demands - leads to a peer-to-peer relationship between the RIs that is enabled via federation capabilities (e.g. the registry of catalogues) to be delivered by the EOSC EU Node (Figure 1). In general, the EOSC EU Node will provide support capabilities to enable federation in EOSC and other scoped collaborations between RIs.

¹ <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/Metadata+Working+Group>

² <https://force11.org/info/the-fair-data-principles/>

³ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/european-research-infrastructures/eric_en

⁴ Although the bi-directional communication with the EOSC Federated Catalogue has been fully implemented, currently the functionality to retrieve resources from this catalogue is still used in a limited manner.

A Federated Search approach

Figure 1 Nodes and EOSC Federated Search capabilities can enrich current EOSC Platform search capabilities.

4 Required Metadata

MWG gathered experts from the RIs within the clusters and representatives of the clusters, to discuss requirements for the metadata in such a peer-to-peer approach infrastructure. After much discussion involving a large number of people and many meetings and internal documents, a proposed metadata element set to describe portals and catalogs was produced. This proposed schema supports the requirement for a zone or 'mall' in the EOSC 'catalog' and is provided at ANNEX1: detailed specification of metadata required.

A further analysis is needed to understand how to merge the new metadata elements proposed in this document to the current EOSC Profiles, evolving them accordingly. We see the current EOSC Association especially the Interoperability Taskforce⁵ as one of the initiatives that can continue providing community input on the metadata infrastructure topic in this process⁶.

5 Acknowledgements

MWG – and particularly the leaders, Keith Jeffery and Daan Broeder – acknowledge the constructive discussions with the EOSC-Future WP3 Architecture team.

Since the work of MWG started - related to the state of the EOSC architecture and metadata profiles at that time - there has been progress. Harvesting involving OpenAIRE is part of the metadata publishing strategy for some individual thematic data centres and RIs (and this is the strategic direction of the ESCAPE cluster). The specification of the profiles has changed markedly, with a hierarchic structure of general profiles and sub-profiles. It has been suggested by EOSC Architecture management that the requirements outlined by the MWG on behalf of the RIs in the clusters could be accommodated in the evolved architecture. This will need analysis and evaluation by the MWG and such work is perhaps best done in the follow-on projects such as EOSC-Beyond.

⁵ <https://eoscfuture.eu/advisory-groups/semantic-interoperability>

⁶ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1a8JKtGkOa_ooTIQJhNHn8bDNH7hWjSK8/view

Appendix A – detailed specification of metadata required

A simple ontology for Portals and Catalogues

We need to be able to describe the relations between and attributes of the following entities:

- Organisation type (RoR): responsible for operating a Portal and/or Catalogue; (Education, Healthcare, Company, Archive, Nonprofit, Government, Facility)
- Organisational purpose: responsible for operating a Portal and/or Catalogue; for example the Re3data type vocabulary for organisations (disciplinary, governmental, interdisciplinary, institutional, project related, other)
- Research discipline: FRASCATI, and the FAIRsharing subject ontology for all disciplines, and others, crosswalks to be provided
- Research infrastructure: ESFRI list as a core; supplemented by all relevant cluster RIs
- Portal: a website allowing users to find (partially through a catalogue) and access services and data, based on Portal URL?,
- Catalogue: a browsable/searchable list of services and/or data, based on catalog URL?

The required elements (attributes or linked entities with attributes) for a Portal and Catalog are:

Portal:

- Name (1,m) (String/identifier)
- Acronym (1,m) (String/identifier)
- URL (1,m) (portal landing page)
- Description (n,m) (abstract), supporting multilingual descriptions
- Location: Country, region, city: (n,m) (tuples of String/identifier) also labels “distributed”, and “undefined” are allowed to indicate explicit intend not to be connected to a physical location
- Link-Related organisations (n,m) (with roles: responsible, operator, funder, ...) note that for comparison reasons the organisation links should be standardised or else we should use tuples of standardised name and a link (name, link), cross-check with EOSC profile
- Link-Related (n,m) (tuples of String/identifier) (person) contacts (not necessarily persons, helpdesk/contact email will do) cross-check with EOSC profile
- Portal type: (n,m) (website only, hosting and providing data access, providing services, aggregating metadata,...)

Service:

- Eg. training platform with online training facilities using its own catalog of training materials. To be discussed if necessary to define in this document

Catalogue:

- Name (1,m) (String/identifier)

- Acronym: (1,m) (String/identifier)
- URL: (1,m) (portal landing page)
- Description (abstract): (n,m) (abstract)
- Domain specification using values from and link to Research discipline thesaurus (using what: Frascati? UDC?, LoC?): (n,m)
- Subject keywords from a defined thesaurus, eg. based on catalogue record metadata (n,m)
- Free text keywords (n,o)
- Spatial coordinates related to the main subject of the catalogue (n,o)
- Temporal coordinates related to the main subject of the catalogue (n,o)
- Acknowledgement mechanism e.g. citation for use of catalogue and digital assets (m,o)
- Catalogue usage type (n,m)
- Digital Asset access type (n,m)
- Link-Related organisations (n,m) (tuples) (with roles: responsible, operator, funder, ...) note that for comparison reasons the organisation links should be standardised or else we should use tuples of standardised name and a link (name, link), cross-check with EOSC profile,
- Link-Related (n,m) (tuples) (person) contacts (not necessarily persons, helpdesk/contact email will do) cross-check with EOSC profile, inheriting Portal information by default vocabularies

Portal type, multiple values may be provided:

- project portal represents the work of a project with limited life-span
- institute portal represents the work of an institute's and is meant to offer information and services for internal and external users for indefinite time
- distributed collaborative organisation that offers information and services for users for indefinite time
- information only (note such a Portal would not have a catalogue eg. a blog)
- (aggregated) metadata only
- data and services

Catalog usage type, multiple values may be provided.

- List "the catalog is a simple list of digital asset descriptions"
- Faceted search UI " the catalogue offers a faceted search interface for searching and selecting metadata records,
- API "the catalogue offers an API for searching metadata records"
- Harvestable "the metadata records can be harvested using a suitable protocol eg. OAI-PMH
- Available for federated-search

Digital Asset access type (not considering creation or update of records), multiple values may be provided:

- Free
 - Free access and download via catalog provided URI

- Free access via Portal provided service (no download)
- Specific License
 - Free access academic via academic FIM authentication
 - Restricted access via academic FIM authentication
 - Restricted access via click-through ToU and registration
 - Restricted access of machines via security token enabled API
 - Special request to be submitted before access is granted
- Costs involved
 - Commercial access to be negotiated with hosting organisation

[Access usually is subject to end-user agreement to terms and conditions, personal data privacy conditions (GDPR) and choice of cookies]

This needs further discussion ie. will consider mapping this detailed list on the smaller set: (1) free for all, or academic use, (2) specific license / conditions, (3) costs involved

Research Infrastructure roles, multiple values may be provided,

- Institutional, catalogue is providing information on hosted digital assets only
- national, catalogue designated for providing information for a specific country
- part of RI, catalogue is considered part of the named RI providing information (especially also) on non-hosted digital assets
- using RI, catalogue is using/harvesting metadata provided by named RI
- part of cluster, catalogue is considered part of the named cluster RI providing information (especially also) on non-hosted digital assets

Some notes on aspects still to be clarified:

How to represent the metadata? A flat list is probably not most suitable since some structure needs to be expressed: Portal <-> Catalog relation, Portal/Catalog <-> organisation/role relations

- Fully connected graph (SKG), probably most neat but in which case we need stable URIs, can we use provisional URIs, but see also the CERIF example using (internal) UUIDs
- Flat record structure: needs some hacks for flattening the structure and much syntactic and semantic information lost
- Hierarchic record structure: as XSD/XML most easy but not representing accurately the fully connected graph

English is the default language for specifying values of cardinality 1